

EVALUATION OF DAMAGE PROPAGATION OF MARINE COMPOSITES UNDER POST-IMPACT FATIGUE

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Abstract

Impact damage and post-impact behavior through fatigue condition of CFRP laminates for marine use were evaluated. Also the effects of water absorption on these properties were considered. Materials used were plain woven T300B-3K CFRP laminates and multi-axial knitted T700S-12K CFRP laminates. Matrix resin of both CFRP laminates was vinylester. CFRP laminates were molded by VARTM method. Compression after impact (CAI) and post-impact fatigue (PIF) properties were evaluated on coupon specimens, which were applied the impact energy (1 J per unit thickness) CAI and PIF strength of 'Dry' and 'Wet (specimen soaked in the water)' specimen of plain woven CFRP showed almost same values. Therefore for T300B plain woven CFRP laminates, the effect of water absorption on PIF properties was small. On the other hand, multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates showed large effect of water absorption, and Wet specimens showed lower PIF properties than Dry ones. However, net CAI and PIF strengths of multi-axial knitted CFRP were larger than that of plain woven CFRP. This study was supported by the Office of Naval Research (award No.: N000140110949).

1 Introduction

When composites are applied to large-scale structures such as ships, the number of stacking layer becomes larger with conventional thin prepreg or woven fabric, thus long time to molding, labor and cost are necessary. In order to clear these problems, multi-axial knitted fabric which has comparatively thickness and no-crimp is focused as one of new-style reinforcement fabric [1-5]. This fabric has the characteristic configuration in which fiber layers aligned in multi-axial direction are stacked and knitted each other. Therefore thickness

and fiber alignment can be obtained with less number of stacking. Additionally, it is thought that no-crimp configuration appears excellent mechanical properties of reinforcement fibers easier than conventional woven fabric etc. On the other hand, as the molding method to be able to facilitate and reduce the price of molding composite for large-scale structures by combining with multi-axial knitted fabric, vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) method is paid to attention. Because VARTM does not need the closed mold and pressurized device to the resin either, VARTM is expected as a highly accurate molding method that takes the place of a conventional RTM. Besides, objective large-scale structures are affected by the environment such as variable temperature and humid. The studies of the effect of temperature of polymer composite materials have been conducted [6,7].

In this study, the impact damage and its propagation behavior under fatigue loading and water environment of T300-3K plain woven and T700S-12K multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates were discussed. Matrix resin was vinylester, and the molding method was vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). The damage mechanism within candidate CFRP laminates was evaluated based on the precise observation. Ultrasonic scanning was conducted as a non-destructive observation method, and the cross-sectional observation was also conducted at multiple sections of laminate. The difference between impact damage morphology of plain woven and multi-axial stitched CFRP laminates was characterized three-dimensionally.

2 Materials and Testing Methods

2.1 Materials

The candidate material is a basic type of plain woven fabric, T300B-3K, and newly developed multi-axial knitted fabric, T700S-12K, both of them

supplied by Toray Industries, Inc. The innovative multi-axial knitted fabric is expected to apply to the thick and large structural component such as marine ships, because it has much thickness than the conventional T300 fabric (Fig. 1 (a)), and good mechanical property is expected by its no-crimp configuration and smooth warping performance. Multi-axial knitted fabric consists of several unidirectional or random-mat layers joined by polyester knitting fibers as shown in Fig. 1 (b). CFRP laminates are molded based on vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), which is suitable molding method for large-scale structures. In VARTM, resin is impregnated into reinforcements by atmospheric pressure, unlike conventional RTM with the pressurized resin pot and the rigid closed mold. Figure 2 shows a schematic image of VARTM setup. Resin firstly flows into a flow medium, and then flows into reinforcements. The driving force of resin flow is atmospheric pressure.

Fig. 1 Schematic images of CFRP laminates used.

Fig. 2 Schematic of vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) setup.

2.2 Impact test

A drop weight with a steel semi-spherical tip was used as an impactor. The weight of the impactor was 1113.5 g and the diameter of the tip was 16 mm. The specimen was mounted between supporting steel plates with a cutout hole 30 mm in diameter, as shown in Fig. 3, and was subjected to impact energy directly using the impactor. Impact loading of 1 J per unit thickness (mm) was applied to the center of the specimen by the impactor. The impact damage in the specimen was observed and characterized by ultrasonic C-scan method and direct cross-section observations.

Fig. 3 Schematic image of a fixture of impact test.

2.3 Compression after impact (CAI) test and post-impact fatigue (PIF) test

Compressive strength after impact (CAI strength) and post-impact fatigue (PIF) properties were evaluated. In this study, CAI and PIF tests were conducted with same level coupon specimens as shown in Fig. 4. Compression and fatigue test were applied by Servopulser EHF-EB100kN-20L (Shimadzu Co., Ltd.). Figure 5 shows a fixture for CAI test. Gauge length of CAI specimen was 50 mm. Test speed of CAI was 1.0 mm/min. In PIF tests, stress ratio R was -1 , that is, tension-compression test.

Stress amplitude in PIF tests was decided based on CAI strength as follows; 88 %, 85 % and 80 % of CAI strength for multi-axial knitted CFRP, and 80 %, 70 % and 60 % for plain woven CFRP, respectively. Because multi-axial knitted CFRP showed higher PIF performance, stress amplitude was set in higher level than that of plain woven one.

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Fig. 4 Dimension of the specimen.

Fig. 5 Fixture of CAI test.

2.4 Water absorption condition

The effect of water absorption on CAI and PIF strength of CFRP laminates for marine use was evaluated with specimens immersed water bath. Same level coupon specimens as well as normal dry CAI and PIF tests were used for water absorbed CAI and PIF tests. In order to absorb water to specimens up to saturation water content, the accelerated water absorption tests were conducted as shown in Fig. 6. Based on these tests, water absorption conditions were decided as follows; both multi-axial knitted and plain woven CFRP specimens were soaked in a water bath at 95°C for 120 hours up to saturation water content of 0.6wt%. After absorption of water, same level impact (1 J per unit thickness) was applied to these specimens. Specimens after soaking were named as “Wet”, as contrasted with “Dry” ones. In order to keep the water content of Wet specimen through the PIF test, gauge region of specimen was covered by plastic bag and filled with water inside of it, as shown in Fig. 7. Stress amplitude in PIF tests was 80 %, 70 % and 60 % for both multi-axial knitted and plain woven CFRP.

Fig. 6 Water content versus time.

3 Approach to Evaluate Damages

3.1 Non-destructive evaluation

Damage progress behavior was observed from the opposite side of impact side of specimens by ultrasonic scanning (UT-2000, Toray Engineering Co., Ltd.). Ultrasonic scanning (C-scan) can observe internal damage distribution, especially delamination. C-scan produces an image showing the shape, size, location, and depth of delamination. In this study, the frequency of the transducer was 7.5 MHz.

Fig. 7 Configuration of Wet specimen.

3.2 Direct observations

Multiple cross-sections of the same laminate as observed by C-scan, were observed by optical microscope. A square portion with 30-mm sides and with the impact point as the center was cut and embedded in resin to facilitate easy grinding and polishing of the cross section of the laminate. After curing the resin, the face normal to the cross section of the laminate was ground using No. 320 sandpaper, and polished using 9 μm, 3 μm and 1 μm diamond slurry stepwise using a precision polishing machine (TegraPol-15, Struers Co., Ltd.). The mirror-finished

cross-section was scanned using a blue-ray microscope (VL2000D, LaserTech Co., Ltd.).

Fig. 8 Methodology of the three-dimensional characterization of the impact damage inside laminate.

Fig. 9 Ultrasonic C-scan images of impacted woven CFRP laminate.

Fig. 10 Cross-sectional photographs of plain woven CFRP laminate observed at each section.

3.3 Three-dimensional characterization of the impact damage within laminate

In order to characterize the impact damage on CFRP laminate, both images observed by ultrasonic C-scan device and cross-sectional observation were compared and integrated as shown in Fig. 8. This figure shows the flow in the characterization methodology of the impact damage on CFRP laminate. Both observation methods give different plain information each other about the impact damage, and information obtained is evaluated synthetically. Finally the three-dimensional damage distribution image is estimated.

4 Impact damage in CFRP laminates

4.1 Plain woven CFRP laminate

Ultrasonic C-scan images of damaged area of woven CFRP laminates are shown in Fig. 9. Center of these figures is impact point. Images near the impacted face such as (a) and (b) showed the cross-shaped damage area. Damaged area became smaller near the bottom side. Figure 10 shows the cross-sectional images of woven CFRP laminates. Delaminations and some cracks are clearly shown in these images, and it is clear that the damaged area containing delaminations and cracks decreases with separating from the impact point. Both ultrasonic C-scan images and cross-sectional images observed by optical microscope were compared in Fig. 11. In this figure, cross-sectional images were divided in three-parts as upper, middle and lower, and each part was compared with C-scan image observed at the same depth of laminate. Consequently the damage distribution observed by optical microscope corresponded with that observed by ultrasonic C-scan. More precise observation on the cross-sectional images in Fig. 12 enables to classify the damages included in each section, that is, delaminations and cracks which are hardly to be detected by non-destructive evaluation facilities can be classified.

4.2 Multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate

Ultrasonic C-scan images of the impact damaged multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate were shown in Fig. 12. Here the impact point is the center

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Fig. 11 Comparison of the damage distribution images observed by optical microscope and ultrasonic scanning.

of these images. Ultrasonic scanning was conducted to the 5 different depths of a laminate. Although till the depth 0.25mm, damage was not detected as shown in Fig. 12 (a), two fan-shaped damages which spread in the 0° direction symmetrically considering the impact point were recognized at the depth

0.75mm (Fig. 12 (b)). At the depth 1.75mm (Fig. 12 (c)) damages spread in the 90° direction, and damage spreading direction changed in 0° direction again at the bottom side of laminate as shown in Fig. 12 (d). Accordingly, the damage area detected by ultrasonic C-scan might spread along the direction of fiber bundle which constitutes each layer.

Fig. 12 Ultrasonic C-scan images of multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate after impact test.

A cross-sectional photograph at the section under impact point was shown in Fig. 13 (a). The impact energy was applied from upper side of the photograph, and this section is normal to the 0° fiber bundles. Figure 13 (b) is the enlargement of Fig. 13 (a). From this figure, it is clear that multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate consists of four layers as shown in the left side of the photograph. In addition, transverse cracks occurred through the 0° fiber bundles of 2nd layer and 3rd layer, and long delaminations were observed between 0° and 90° fiber bundles of 3rd layer. Transverse cracks stopped at the boundary between 0° and 90° fiber bundles of 3rd layer. Delaminations occurred from the edge of transverse cracks, and delamination between 0° and 90° fiber bundles of 3rd layer occurred from near the impact point to the end of section observed.

Both ultrasonic C-scan images and cross-sectional images observed by optical microscope were compared in Fig. 14. In this figure, cross-sectional images were divided in three-parts as upper, middle and bottom as shown in Fig. 14 (a), and each part was compared with ultrasonic C-scan images as shown in Fig. 14 (b). Consequently correspondence between the damage distribution observed by optical microscope and ultrasonic C-scan images was recognized. However, especially in upper and middle parts, delamination area observed in cross-sections was larger than that in ultrasonic C-scan images. This fact means that the damage, especially delamination, observed by ultrasonic C-scan was comparatively thick ones, and thin delamination was not detected. Further between of upper and middle delaminations, multiple transverse cracks existed, and they must affect on the damage tolerance performance of CFRP laminate.

(a) photograph of cross-section under impact point

(b) enlargement around the impact point

Fig. 13 Cross-sectional photographs observed at the impact point.

(a) distribution of delamination area

Upper layer

Middle layer

Bottom layer

(b) ultrasonic C-scan images corresponding to the damage distribution observed in the cross-sections

Fig. 14 Comparison between damage areas obtained by the cross-sectional observation and the ultrasonic C-scan.

4.3 Three-dimensional characterization of impact damage within CFRP laminates

Figure 15 shows the three dimensional images estimated by the cross-sectional images of the impact damage on plain woven and multi-axial stitched CFRP laminates. Because transverse cracks of plain woven CFRP laminate were observed intensively in the upper layers at the section under impact point and that distant from the impact point 3.0mm, it is estimated that cracks exist intensively in the area of circle with a radius of about 3mm. In addition, it was recognized from ultrasonic C-scan images that the damage near the impact point spread in the circle form centering on the impact point. Therefore it is estimated that transverse cracks are distributed in the shape of a cone centering on the

impact point in the upper layers as shown in Fig. 15 (a). Delamination is distributed over a cross shape in the upper layers, and becomes large gradually as a layer becomes deep except in 9th layer where the distribution of delamination forms circle shape. On the other hand, transverse cracks of multi-axial stitched CFRP laminate were distributed in the 0° fiber bundles of 2nd layer and 3rd layer under delamination between 0° and 90° fiber bundles of 3rd layer, and they form cones centering on the impact point as shown in Fig. 15 (b). Delamination spread by turns in 0° and 90° direction along the direction of fiber bundle which constitutes each layer. Delamination occurred between 0° and 90° fiber bundles in 2nd, 3rd and 4th layer, and the direction of delamination depends on the direction of the fiber bundle beneath the delamination.

Fig. 15 Three-dimensional images estimated by the cross-sectional observation of the impact damage on CFRP laminates.

5 Effect of water absorption on post-impact fatigue properties

Figure 16 shows the compressive strength of plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP. Here, the specimens without impact damage were named as “bulk” ones, and plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP were described as “PW” and “MA”, respectively. From this graph, the compressive strength of bulk plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP decreased in 59 % and 66 % by the impact damage, respectively. On the other hand, CAI strength of Wet plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP were 4.4 % and 7.7 % lower respectively than that of Dry ones. Consequently, the effect of water absorption on CAI strength was little.

Figure 17 shows the result of PIF tests of both plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates. All S-N curves in this figure showed approximately inverse linear relation. Both CAI and PIF strength of Dry multi-axial knitted CFRP were higher than that of the other specimens. Slope of approximation line of multi-axial knitted CFRP was smaller than that of plain woven CFRP. Stress amplitude level of Dry multi-axial knitted CFRP was higher than that of Dry plain woven CFRP. Consequently, it is obvious that fatigue performance of MA Dry is fairly higher than that of the others.

Fig. 17 Fatigue strength under water absorption condition of plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates.

5.1 Plain woven CFRP laminates

For damage propagation observation, specimens were stopped at the cycle just before failure for Dry and Wet conditions, respectively. Here, we measured the stroke variations and also ‘the sound of fiber breakage’ for helping to determine the ‘cycle just before failure’. Fig. 18

shows ultrasonic C-scan images of both Dry and Wet specimens before and after fatigue tests. Load was applied in perpendicular direction in these images. In these images, damage propagation was not detected comparing with damage caused by impact only. Actually, plain woven CFRP laminate specimens showed sudden failure at the impact point in the final stage of PIF tests, and almost no-signs were observed before failure.

Fig. 18 Damage propagation shown in ultrasonic C-scan images of plain woven CFRP laminate.

Fig. 19 Damage propagation shown in cross-sectional photographs of plain woven CFRP laminate.

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Figure 19 shows cross-sectional photographs of both Dry and Wet specimens before and after fatigue tests. Cross-sections observed were along the loading direction, that is the perpendicular direction in the ultrasonic scanning images shown in Fig. 18. The increase of delamination was observed along the through-thickness direction in the cross-sections. Cracks propagated from the edge of delamination, or in the fiber bundles as the transverse cracks. However, clear difference of damage morphology between Dry and Wet was not observed.

Fig. 20 Damage propagation shown in ultrasonic C-scan images of multi axial knitted CFRP laminate.

5.2 Multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates

Figure 20 shows the ultrasonic C-scan images before and after fatigue test, respectively. Load was applied in perpendicular direction in these images. It is clear that the damage propagated in load direction in both Dry and Wet. However, this large delamination in loading direction propagated just after starting of fatigue test in the back side of impact side. Therefore it is premature to determine that only this large delamination is the damage propagated by fatigue, thus it is not enough to observe damages only with ultrasonic scanning. Final failure occurred in horizontal direction centering on the impact point.

Figure 21 shows cross-sectional photographs of both Dry and Wet specimens before and after fatigue tests. Cross-sections observed were along the

loading direction, that is the perpendicular direction in the ultrasonic scanning images shown in Fig. 20. The increase of transverse crack was dominant damage in the cross-section of both Dry and Wet specimen in PIF tests. On the other hand, delamination growth was little. The difference of damage morphology between Dry and Wet was not clear.

Fig. 21 Damage propagation shown in cross-sectional photographs of multi-axial knitted CFRP laminate.

5.3 Difference of dominant damage morphology between plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP

The difference of damage propagation morphology between plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates are summarized as illustrated in Fig. 22. In the plain woven CFRP, the increase of delamination in the through-thickness direction is dominant (Fig. 22 (a)). On the other hand, the increase of transverse crack is dominant in the multi-axial knitted CFRP (Fig. 22 (b)). These differences may depend on the reinforcement configuration. In the plain woven CFRP, it is thought that delamination caused by impact was divided in several parts by the crimps of woven bundles, thus its growth in the longitudinal direction was also prevented. Therefore the growth of delamination in the through-thickness direction may

be started from (the edge of) these transverse cracks. On the other hand, transverse cracks easily occurred in the perpendicular fiber bundles in the multi-axial knitted CFRP, because the perpendicular fiber bundles conglomerated in this case of stacking sequence.

Fig. 22 Schematic images of the difference of damage propagation behavior between plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP.

6 Conclusions

In this study, the damage tolerance performance of CFRP laminates for marine use was evaluated. For this purpose, the impact damage mechanism and its propagation behavior of T300 plain woven and T700 multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates were observed by non-destructive and destructive observation methods. Each image observed by these approaches was integrated and ‘three-dimensional’ damage distribution images were obtained. In PIF tests, plain woven CFRP laminates showed sudden failure at the impact point in the final stage of PIF tests, and almost no-signs were observed before failure. On the other hand, in multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates, the damage propagation behavior was observed by proposed observation methods, and the damage distribution under fatigue loading was clarified.

The effect of water absorption on the PIF properties of both plain woven and multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates was evaluated. CAI strength and PIF property of plain woven CFRP were not affected by water absorption condition. However, multi-axial knitted CFRP laminates showed large

effect of water absorption, and Wet specimens showed lower PIF properties than Dry ones.

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